

STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP 10

Milbourn T. Esparagoza MTE, Precious L. Abella Ph.D., Robino A. Silva Jr.

Lun Padidu National High School, Sarangani, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to develop strategic intervention material in Entrepreneurship 10 as intervention to the least learned competencies and challenges of learners in Entrepreneurship 10. The study was both quantitative and qualitative in nature using document analysis to determine the least learned competencies in Entrepreneurship 10 for first and second quarter and semi-structured interview to gather the challenges of grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies. Data revealed that in the first quarter, Grade 10 learners of Lun Padidu National High School for SY 2023-2024 have difficulties in learning the competencies on managing product or service development production and introducing product or service to the market according to marketing plan and clients feedback. In the second quarter, the least learned competencies are conducting product or service trial run based on the operational plan of the business and setting target market and project sales of product and/or services. From the interview on the challenges experienced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies, three themes emerged: numerical complexity, lack of interest and low understanding of the concepts. Based on the result, Strategic Intervention Material in Entrepreneurship 10 is needed to bridge the gap of learning by providing opportunities for practice, review, and application, leading to mastery of skills and concepts.

Keywords: *intervention, least learned competencies, Entrepreneurship*

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the most significant investments a nation can make in its future. It is a powerful driving force of change as it contributes to the long-term development, growth and progress of one's country.

Education is a fundamental right but in 2020 it was disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic. In response to the urgent need to recover education from prolonged disruptions, RAPID framework for Learning Recovery and Acceleration is introduced.

The framework encapsulates five key actions to recover learning: Reach every child and keep them in school; Assess learning levels regularly; Prioritize teaching the fundamentals; Increase the efficiency of instruction, including through catch-up learning; and develop psychosocial health and wellbeing (UNICEF, 2023). In the Philippines, Department of Education adopts the National Learning Recovery Program to address the learning loss heightened by school closures and disruption as well as the low performance of learners in International Large-Scale Assessments and national assessments (DepEd Order No.13, s. 2023). MATATAG Agenda was launched by the Department of Education as the new direction towards improving the quality of basic education in the country which includes the implementation of the revised curriculum known as the MATATAG Curriculum. The MATATAG Curriculum has the following features: decongested curriculum, focus on foundational skills, balanced cognitive demands, clearer articulation of 21st-century skills, reduced learning areas, intensified Values Education and Peace Education, and on a par with international standards (DepEd Memorandum No. 53, s. 2023).

Entrepreneurship as a driving force of economic growth of nations resulted to the incorporation of entrepreneurship as a subject in the education system. However, entrepreneurship Education in the Philippines is more focused in developing people for employment rather than entrepreneurship. Another weakness is the lack of Filipino role models in the form of entrepreneurs promoting high opportunity-high growth undertaking since the education system is highly patterned after that of the United States of America. There is also lack of materials to support entrepreneurial education in terms of cases that focus on local context of business (Velasco, 2013).

Academic performance of the learners can be gauged through their mean percentage score (MPS) in the examination. Records show that the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of Lun Padidu National High School (LPNHS) in Entrepreneurship 10 is 64.41, 51.16 and 65.76 for school year 2020-2021, 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 respectively (Guidance Counselor Records, 2022). The gathered data revealed that Entrepreneurship 10 reflects MPS below the passing rate of 75% in a 100% MPS percentage which implies that learners have least learned competencies. Informal interview with Technical Vocational Coordinator of LPNHS revealed that learners experience difficulties learning certain concepts in the subject.

With this, the data and arguments above pushed the researchers to conduct this research to develop instructional material as intervention to the least learned competencies and challenges of learners in Entrepreneurship 10. The Strategic Intervention Materials for Entrepreneurship 10 will provide opportunities for practice, review, and application, leading to mastery of skills and concepts of learners. It serves to reinforce lessons that may not be fully understood by learners, aiding them in achieving proficiency in the skills being taught.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop strategic intervention material in Entrepreneurship 10 by determining the least learned competencies and challenges of Grade 10 Learners for first and second grading in Entrepreneurship in Lun Padidu National High School for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the least learned competencies in Entrepreneurship of Grade 10 learners?

2. What are the challenges faced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies in Entrepreneurship? and
3. Based on the results, what intervention material can be developed?

METHODOLOGY

The research design was descriptive that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon that is being studied (Manjunatha, 2019) utilizing quantitative and qualitative data. The participants of the study are ten (10) Grade 10 learners of Lun Padidu National High School for the SY 2023-2024.

The first instrument was document analysis on the least learned competencies of Grade 10 learners covering the first and second quarter of Entrepreneurship 10. The last instrument was interview guide for grade 10 learners. It contained list of questions focusing on the challenges encountered by the learners in terms of least learned competencies in Entrepreneurship for first and second quarter of 2023-2024. Document analysis and interview schedules were developed by the researchers and validated by three experts. The usual process of validation was used to establish the congruence of the items in the instruments with the statement of the problem. Three experts was requested to serve as validators. Validation sheet was utilized to establish the validity of the instruments. Comments and suggestions of the three validators were incorporated and the final form was checked by grammarian for possible grammatical lapses.

In finding the solution in research question 1, the researchers employed document analysis. In determining the answer in research question number 2, the researchers employed the Braun & Clarke's (2006) 6-step framework to identify useful themes from the semi structured interview on the challenges of Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies. In finding the answer in research question number 3, the researchers presented, analyzed and interpreted the data gathered which serve as the guide in formulating strategic intervention material that presented the concepts and topics in different formats and encouraged the learners to explore and analyze knowledge in meaningful ways to promote deeper engagement in the lessons thereby increasing the academic achievement of learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This portion covers the results and discussions concerning the least learned competencies and challenges of Grade 10 learners in Entrepreneurship 10 to develop an intervention material. The order of the discussion followed the sequence of the research questions.

Least Learned Competencies in Entrepreneurship 10

From the document analysis, the least learned competencies of Entrepreneurship 10 for first and second quarter is presented below.

Table 1: Least Learned Competencies of Entrepreneurship 10 For First And Second Quarter

Quarter	Competency
First	1. Manage product or service development production
	2. Introduces product or service to the market according to marketing plan and clients feedback
Second	1. Conduct product or service trial run based on the operational plan of the business
	2. Sets target market and project sales of product and/or services.

In the first quarter, Grade 10 learners of Lun Padidu National High School for SY 2023-2024 have difficulties in learning the competencies on managing product or service development production and introducing product or service to the market according to marketing plan and clients feedback. In the second quarter, the least learned competencies are conducting product or service trial run based on the operational plan of the business and setting target market and project sales of product and/or services. The data revealed that learners have low mastery of concepts on the competencies reflected in Table 1. De Jesus (2019) pointed that lack of content of mastery of the lessons indicates academic underachievement.

The result of the study is similar to the findings of Almeida and Buzady (2019) that the focus group performance was lower in terms of business oriented thinking and prioritizing. These indicate that students attending the entrepreneurship course show less ability to look at business from the customer's perspective and assume greater capacity to evaluate risks in the business of their decisions and performed calculated decisions.

Challenges Experienced by Grade 10 learners in terms of Least Learned Competencies in Entrepreneurship

From the interview on the challenges experienced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies, three themes emerged: numerical complexity, lack of interest and low understanding of the concepts.

Table 2. Thematic Statements and Essential Themes on challenges experienced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies

Thematic Statements	Essential Themes
All of the participants revealed that they have difficulty dealing with numbers.	Numerical Complexity
All of the participants stated that they are not interested in the subject/lessons.	Lack of Interest
Most of the participants stated that they have low level understanding on the concepts.	Low understanding of the Concept

Numerical Complexity

From the interview conducted, it was revealed that one of the challenges faced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies is the numerical complexity. These are reflected in the following statements:

SP-1: I find it difficult because there are times I get confused especially with numbers.
 SP-2: It is hard for me because I need to count how many stocks are left.
 SP-3: During Entrep I feel the subject is difficult because you have to solve the unit price, volume cost and volume target.
 SP-4: I find it hard because it talk about finances such as loan, debt, profit.
 SP-5: In the discussion I get confused sometimes when the topic is about solving like income and expenses.
 SP-6: It is bit hard when it comes to solving and computing since I am not good in Math.
 SP-7: It is hard because we have to compute and use formula.
 SP-8: During the activity, I find it difficult when I'm solving the problem
 SP-9: It is not easy to compute what should be the price of our product or the costing.
 SP-10: I also like the computation even it is a difficult task.

Participants revealed that it is difficult to learn Entrepreneurship because they have to engage in activities and tasks that involves numbers. The results of research conducted by Rameli and Rustam (2016) indicated that learning mathematics was perceived as difficult by students as too many formulas need to be memorized, too many concepts involved in order to solve mathematical problem and respondents experienced examination pressure because they think that they need to apply a lot of knowledge and skills learned to excel in the evaluation. Peteros, Gamboa, Etcuban, Dinauanao, Sitoy and Arcadio (2020) revealed in their study that the students had low self-concept on the perception that they understand Mathematics even the most difficult ones and that every question in Mathematics is answerable. This low level of the respondents' self-concept could be based on their experiences that they were not able to solve severe problems in Mathematics and that they think that not all these problems have answers.

Lack of Interest

From the gathered data, it was revealed that one of the challenges faced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies is the lack of interest in the subject. Learners find it difficult to understand the lessons because they do not like the topic and they cannot relate to it. These are shown in the following statements:

SP-1: It is hard for me since I am not interested in Entrep.
 SP-2: I find the subject difficult because I do not like the topic which is about business plan.
 SP-5: For me, Entrepreneurship is hard because it is about business and I am not interested in business.
 SP-7: I cannot relate to the topic because it concerns business which I do not like.
 SP-8: Entrep for me is hard since it talks about business which I cannot relate to.

Others learners showed that they are not interested in Entrepreneurship by not being active, attentive and focused to the teaching-learning process as reflected in their statements.

SP-3: During our class, I do not really focus on the discussions and activities.
 SP-4: I do not listen and focus to the discussion in Entrep.
 SP-10: When we are having the discussion, I am not that attentive to the teacher.

SP-9: In the class activities I am not active because I do not like to engage in business in the future.

Learners find it difficult to master the concepts in Entrepreneurship 10 because of the absence of interest in the subject itself. Farid and Rahman (2020) stated in their study that learners have lack of interest in university entrepreneurship program. It has been reported that some students show low favorable attitude towards being tied with the university's entrepreneurship agenda. On the other hand, Rone, Guao, Jariol, Acedillo, Balinton and Francisco (2023) mentioned that the presence of motivation in the classroom setting has been the backbone of the learning process. According to the results of their study, there is lack of motivation and engagement of the learners in the classroom and learners have the mindset to play/talk to their classmates around the classroom rather than listen to the teachers' lesson.

Low understanding of the concept of entrepreneurship

The data revealed that the Grade 10 learners have low understanding of the concept in Entrepreneurship and this is shown in the following statements.

SP-1: For me the lessons are difficult because I cannot understand the lessons fully.

SP-3: During the discussion I cannot understand the lessons because of the terms or words which is not easy to understand.

SP-5: My understanding on the lessons is basic only which makes me slow when it comes to activities.

SP-6: There are times when I struggle to understand the lessons because of the terminologies which are difficult to understand.

SP-8: During the Entrep sometimes I get confuse because I cannot follow easily the discussion of the certain topic.

SP-9. There are times that I'm feeling lost during the activity and discussion.

Learners' comprehension of the concept is limited and suggests that there is gap in the mastery of concepts. Farid and Rahman (2020) stated that lack of understanding on important concepts in entrepreneurship activities, such as the concept of business cooperatives or social entrepreneurship have been reported as unpleasant issues which affect participants' motivation to involve in entrepreneurship activities.

Intervention Material

From the least learned competencies in the first and second quarter in Entrepreneurship 10 and challenges of the learners, a Strategic Intervention Materials for Entrepreneurship 10 was developed. It is a form of intervention for the grade 10 learners to master the least learned competencies in the first and second quarters in Entrepreneurship 10 to increase their level of understanding. Before the learners can apply their knowledge on series of activities and exercises, concepts were presented first in easy manner for the learners to grasp the idea.

The Strategic Intervention material is contextualized and localized integrating names of local businessman and store owners, nature of business and establishments in the community and nearby places, scenarios and events held that are familiar to students, making the content more relevant, relatable and meaningful. This facilitates students to relate new information to their existing knowledge and experiences and

leading to deeper understanding which may result to increase academic achievement of learners in terms of least learned competencies.

Furthermore, the material has undergone evaluation on the content and grammar through Quality Assurance by the school Quality Assurance Team. Suggestions and recommendations were incorporated in the final manuscript of the intervention material.

Conclusions

From the data gathered, the researchers concluded the following:

1. Grade 10 learners of Lun Padidu National High School for SY 2023-2024 have difficulties in learning the competencies on managing product or service development production and introducing product or service to the market according to marketing plan and clients feedback. In the second quarter, the least learned competencies are conducting product or service trial run based on the operational plan of the business and setting target market and project sales of product and/or services.

2. The challenges experienced by Grade 10 learners in terms of least learned competencies, three themes emerged: numerical complexity, lack of interest and low understanding of the concepts.

3. Development of strategic intervention material for least learned competencies is vital to bridge the gap of learning through mastery of the least learned competencies by providing opportunities for practice, review, and application.

Recommendations

In the context of the findings of the study, the researcher recommends:

1. That teachers need to determine the least learned competencies of learners and are encouraged to develop intervention materials to increase academic achievement of learners in terms of least learned competencies.

2. That teachers need to determine the challenges of learners in learning the concepts as a guide in the development of intervention suited to the needs of the learners.

3. That the Strategic Intervention Material for Entrepreneurship 10 may be adapted for implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author(s) have stated that they have no potential conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. The authors accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed consent was given to each participant before the conduct of the study. The data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

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Based on the recommendations, this action plan was drawn:

ACTION PLAN

Title: Strategic Intervention Material in Entrepreneurship 10

Areas of Concern	Objective/s	Activity/ Strategy	Expected Output	Persons Involved	Time Frame	Fund (Amount) Source: Personal	Remarks
Development of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM)	To identify the least learned competencies	Meet and discuss with the Entrepreneurship 10 teacher and coordinator	Least Learned Competencies	Entrep 10 Teacher TVE Coordinator	January 2024	None	Completed
	To create activity sheets/ worksheets	Meet and plan with developers	Activity Sheets/ worksheets	Researchers	January-February 2024	2,000	Completed
Validation of SIM	To validate the content and grammar	Coordinate with TVE Coordinator to identify possible validators in school level Send request letter for grammar editing	Quality assured SIM (School Level)	School QA Team	February 2024	2,000	Completed
		Coordinate with Division TVE Coordinator to identify possible validators	Quality Assured SIM (Division Level)	Division TVE QA Team	March-May 2024	2,000	On process
Editing of SIM	To incorporate the comments and suggestions of validators of School QA Team Division QA Team	Edit the SIM	Edited SIM (School Level)	Researchers	March 2024	2,000	Completed
			Edited SIM (Division Level)		March-May 2024	2,000	On process
Utilization of SIM	To utilize the developed SIM	Present the SIM during School LAC Session to TVE Teachers	Attendance Sheet	Teachers Principal	SY 2024-2025	None	To accomplish
		TVE teachers used the SIM as supplementary material	Answered activity sheets	Teachers Learners	1 st -2 nd Quarter of 2024-2025	None	To accomplish
		Benchmarking of SIM by other schools	Attendance Sheet	Teachers	Whole year round	None	To accomplish
		Present the SIM to Division LR	Certificate		August 2024	None	To accomplish